

Cationic Graft Copolymerisation of Ethylenimine Using Polymeric Initiator

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The cationic graft copolymerisation of ethylenimine has been carried out by using poly(NAE-co-St) as a initiator and anhydrous ferric chloride as a catalyst. The highest graft percent was obtained with 0.05 M FeCl₃ for 40 min at 50°. A suitable explanation for this observation has been proposed.

REPORTS on the polymerisation of ethylenimine by acids¹⁻³ and other catalysts^{4,5} are extensive but to a large extent are confined to linear polymerisation. The graft copolymerisation of preformed polyethylenimine to starch has only been reported⁶. The aim of the present work is to describe the preparation of graft copolymers with polyethylenimine grafts onto a polystyrene backbone by reacting ethylenimine in the presence of anhydrous ferric chloride with a backbone chain fitted with randomly distributed acryloyl-ethylenimine functions which act as "initiator" (and also as "promotor"). In addition, the purpose of preparing such a graft copolymer is to explain why crosslinking was never observed upon grafting by the above method and to examine the difference of physical properties between linear polymer and graft copolymer. The general procedure is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The introduction of N-acryloyl-ethylenimine (NAE) functions, which are the grafting sites, onto polymer backbone might presumably be possible by the methods shown in Scheme 2. However, path A was inadequate because of the existence of side reaction when handling the sample. Path B was also unsuitable for the reason that gelification (crosslinking) of the reaction medium usually took place during polymerisation. Hence the method, the author

Scheme 2

Path A : Nucleophilic substitution
Path B : Radical polymerization

has attempted, is to adopt styrene as the comonomer of a backbone in order to prevent crosslinking whereon a far more amount of styrene than that of NAE should be used. NAE used as comonomer of a backbone is a heterofunctional monomer with an acrylic double bond, polymerisable by free radical mechanism and an ethylenimine group sensitive to cationic polymerisation.

Experimental

Ethylenimine : Ethylenimine was prepared after the method of Wenker⁷ in 30% yield.

N-Acryloyl-ethylenimine (NAE) : NAE was prepared by adding acryloyl chloride (0.1 mole) at 0° to a solution of ethylenimine (0.2 mole) in ether. The white precipitate was washed with ether, the solution was evaporated, and the residue distilled *in vacuo*, b.p. 21 22/0.4 mm Hg, yield 70%.

Preparation of poly(NAE-co-St) : Poly(NAE-co-St) was obtained by the copolymerisation of NAE and styrene in benzene (20% vol) under nitrogen atmosphere at 65° with azobisisobutyronitrile (1% wt). Poly(NAE-co-St) used as initiator (and also as promotor) was quantitatively obtained by the copolymerisation of two monomers (mole ratio, St : NAE :: 15 : 1) for 24 hr. Poly(NAE-co-St) used in

determining reactivity ratio should be prepared at different molar ratios of two monomers in low conversion (not more than 10% of the mixture). After polymerisation, the copolymer was precipitated with *n*-hexane, filtered, purified by reprecipitation and then dried under reduced pressure for 3 days.

Preparation of grafted polyethylenimine : Ethylenimine (usually 3 ml ; 2.5 g) was placed in a heavy hard glass tube chilled to -78° , avoiding moisture, and powdered poly(NAE-co-St) and anhydrous FeCl_3 were added. After being flushed with dry nitrogen, the glass tube was immediately sealed, agitated, and placed in a constant temperature bath for the appropriate time. After the required reaction time, the tube was opened and rinsed out with a saturated aqueous solution of sodium phosphate to remove the ferric chloride from the polymer. Unreacted ethylenimine was evaporated and the graft copolymer was dried to constant weight *in vacuo* for 3 days. The polymer was refined by dissolving in absolute ethanol and precipitating by pouring into anhydrous ether. Ferric chloride gave essentially quantitative conversion to polymers which were all yellow or brown viscous oils or gums and very hygroscopic. They were soluble in methanol, ethanol and water, and insoluble in ether, acetone, benzene and dioxane.

The graft percent was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Graft percent} = \frac{\text{dry wt. of grafting sample} - \text{dry wt. of original sample}}{\text{dry wt. of original sample}} \times 100$$

The viscosity of the graft copolymer was measured in ethanol at $25 \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ using an Ubbelohde viscometer.

Results and Discussion

Copolymerisation of NAE and styrene :

Since only ethylenimine units contain nitrogen atom, the weight percent of nitrogen can be used to calculate the mole ratio of NAE to styrene in the copolymers. The reactivity ratios, r_1 (for NAE) and r_2 (for St), were determined by the use of Fineman-Ross equation⁸ and found as $r_1 = 1.52$, $r_2 = 0.36$ ($r_1 r_2 = 0.55$).

If we use these values as a qualitative measure of the reactivity ratio of monomers, we can further see the character of NAE by the combination of r_1 and r_2 values with Alfrey-Price equation⁹. For NAE the values of the polarity parameter, e , of 1.61 and the resonance parameter, Q , of 0.43 are obtained. The olefinic center in NAE is highly polar but without appreciable tendency for resonance stabilisation when compared with styrene. We can also see from the product value of r_1 and r_2 that the polymer is random copolymer and thus good a polymeric initiator.

Cationic graft copolymerisation of ethylenimine :

Spectroscopic data of grafted polyethylenimine was similar to linear polyethylenimine because a small amount of poly(NAE-co-St) was probably

used. A trace of moisture seemed to retard the polymerisation.

The mechanism of cationic graft copolymerisation of ethylenimine would be most reasonably explained by $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ type opening of ethylenimine ring^{1,10}. Termination could occur by proton abstraction from the immonium ion by the counterion or nitrogen in the polymer chain or the ethylenimine monomer. A back-biting ring expansion termination with the formation of a relatively unreactive piperazine end group has also been postulated¹¹.

Effect of grafting time :

As can be shown from Table 1, the formation of polyethylenimine branch is initiated during the initial phase of the process (up to 40 min). The growth of the initially formed polyethylenimine branches appears to be the principal reaction. The fall of graft percent after 40 min of the reaction might be due to the degradation of grafted polyethylenimine chain. It is evident that poly(NAE-co-St) is a good polymeric initiator and also promoter in graft copolymerisation of ethylenimine because the opening of ethylenimine ring is facilitated by the introduction of acyl group.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF GRAFTING TIME

Ethylenimine : 1 M ; FeCl_3 : 0.05 M ; Temp. : 50° ; Poly(NAE-co-St) : 1.50 g.

Expt. No.	Grafting time (min)	Grafting (%)
1	20	927
2	30	2244
3	40	2981
4	50	2732

Effect of grafting temperature :

The Table 2 shows that the graft percent increases with augmenting temperature up to 50° , but decreases above that. The likely reasons are (i) degradation of grafted polyethylenimine chain and, (ii) greater rate of termination of the polymer chain.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF GRAFTING TEMPERATURE

Ethylenimine : 1 M ; FeCl_3 : 0.05 M ; Reaction time : 40 min ; Poly(NAE-co-St) : 1.50 g.

Expt. No.	Grafting temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Grafting (%)
1	30	1327
2	40	1963
3	50	2981
4	80	2116
5	100	669

Effect of FeCl_3 concentration :

It is seen from Table 3 that maximum grafting is achieved when the FeCl_3 concentration is 0.05 M. The degree of grafting declined with a rise in FeCl_3 concentration. The viscosity of the graft copolymer also increased up to 0.05 M FeCl_3 concentration

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF FeCl_3 CONCENTRATION ON THE GRAFTING REACTION

Ethylenimine : 1 M ; Temp. : 50° ;
Reaction time : 40 min ; Poly(NAE-co-St) : 1.50 g.

Expt. No.	FeCl_3 $10^2 \times M$	Grafting (%)	Inherent viscosity
1	1	846	0.50
2	2	2438	1.37
3	3	2627	1.43
4	5	2981	1.59
5	6	2543	1.40

and thereafter decreased. It has been known that the increased catalyst concentration gives an increased conversion to polymer, but gives the decreased conversion when relative concentration of FeCl_3 with respect to poly(NAE-co-St) is unfittingly greater. This might be attributed to the homopolymerisation of ethylenimine by FeCl_3 , as a result of which sufficient amount of ethylenimine at the grafting site is absent.

Effect of poly(NAE-co-St) :

The effect of poly(NAE-co-St) on the grafting is shown in Table 4. The graft percent rose up to 1.50 g of poly(NAE-co-St) and subsequently dropped

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF POLY(NAE-co-St)

Ethylenimine : 1 M ; FeCl_3 : 0.05 M ;
Reaction time : 40 min. ; Temp. : 50°.

Expt. No.	Poly(NAE-co-St) (g)	Grafting (%)
1	0.75	982
2	1.00	1943
3	1.25	2427
4	1.50	2981
5	1.75	2732

with further increase of poly(NAE-co-St). It is apparent that the relatively high initiator concentration with respect to catalyst brings about a relative decrease of catalyst concentration and hence gives decreased conversion.

In conclusion, the polymerisation of ethylenimine using poly(NAE-co-St) may be employed as a satisfactory method for the preparation of graft copolymers.

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